

MACE-Seq-Based Transcripts Profilings in Breast Cancer: Tumor Suppressive *miR-1185-p5* Promotes Cell Migration and Invasion by Targeting *BCAS1*, *CASC3*, *GATA2*, and *VOPPI*

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Abstract

Abnormally expressed microRNAs (miRNAs) have been observed to interfere with intracellular RNA mechanisms in breast cancer (BC). Small RNA sequencing of 50 BC and 50 normal adjacent tissue (NAT) was conducted to identify the differential expression of non-coding transcripts. The findings showed that 152 tumor-suppressive and 22 oncogenic miRNAs were identified in BC, compared with NAT. Among these, *miR-1185-5p*, previously unstudied in BC, was found to be downregulated in cancer tissues, and associated with poor prognosis ($P = 0.002$). RT-qPCR of 100 BCs and 100 NATs confirmed the down expression of this miRNA. Low expression of *miR-1185-5p* was significantly associated with poor prognosis in patients with BC (overall survival (OS) rate: $P = 0.002$). Overexpression of *miR-1185-5p* suppressed BC cell migration and invasion via regulating oncogenic genes *BCAS*, *CASC3*, *GATA2*, and *VOPPI*, which are overexpressed in BC tissues and linked to poor prognosis. The overexpression of these in BC tissues was determined using MACE-Seq and Western Blot results. Overexpression of these genes was significantly related to poor prognosis in BC (OS rate: *BCAS1* ($P=0.0033$), *CASC3* ($P=0.005$), *GATA2* ($P=0.006$), and *VOPPI* ($P=0.01$)). These findings highlight *miR-1185-5p*'s potential as a therapeutic target.

Keywords: Breast Cancer, Differentially Gene Expression, Small RNAs, *miR-1185-5p*

Background

Breast cancer (BC) occurs when breast epithelial cells genetically transform into malignant cells, which develop and form tumors. Breast carcinoma is the most global type of cancer incidence in women (23.8%), and is the leading cause of mortality in women (15,4%) (1, 2). BC typically originates in the breast gland cells and is a severe threat to the lives of females, with men accounting for just about 1-2% of breast cancer sufferers (3). BC is responsible for 7-10% of all malignant tumors in humans, trailing only cervical cancer in women. Postmenopausal females aged 40 to 60 are more prevalent. The prevalence of postmenopausal females aged 40 to 60 is higher among them. BC, like a few other forms of tumors, usually takes a long time to develop, and it takes 7 to 8 years for the tumor to grow to the size of a 1 cm sphere (4). Additionally, surgery is the primary curative option for breast cancer, and radiotherapy is one of the local options for therapy. Surgery and radiation alone may heal the great majority of BC cases before tumor metastasis (5). Routine therapy can only cure a tiny fraction of BC cases once they have metastases (6). Moreover, several factors influence the prognosis of BC cases, the most important of which are tumor invasion scope and pathological and biological features. Early recognition and therapy are the most efficient methods to prevent BC death (7).

Frequently, BC is the outcome of a genetic mutation that occurs in breast cells. Whereas around ten percent of BCs are passed down from parents to their children, over eighty-five percent of BCs develop during their lives. Inherited *TP53* and *PTEN* gene mutations were found to increase the likelihood of malignant breast carcinoma growth (8). Recently, analysis of gene expression has played an important role in the therapeutical selection of BC subtypes. The gene expression measurement can be utilized to classify BC subtypes on a molecular level. According to two investigations, this classification makes determining curative doses easier. BC molecular subtypes include luminal-A, luminal-B (including HER2+ /), HER2+, and triple-negative (TN). These subgroups are critical for treatment selection and are linked to BC's biological aspects (9).

If a cancer patient is diagnosed before distant metastasis, the overall cancer survival rate improves significantly. Biomarker analysis could circumvent the restrictions of imaging modalities whilst allowing for early illness recognition. In this regard, the human epidermal growth factor receptor

2 (HER2), KI-67 protein, and estrogen receptors (ERs) are commonly employed for prognosis and therapeutic advice (10). Recently, microRNAs (miRNAs) are another possible biomarker of breast cancer that has gained traction. miRNAs are non-coding short RNA molecules of 21-25 nucleotides that regulate target proteins (11, 12).

Research indicates that small RNA molecules from the human genome play important roles in cellular functions such as proliferation, motility, and death (13, 14). Among the small RNAs, microRNAs (miRNAs) are small single-stranded RNA molecules (19-22 nucleotide) that act as post-transcriptional gene regulators in a variety of biological functions. Broadly, miRNAs modulate mRNA transcripts by joining to their specific messenger RNAs (mRNAs), resulting in either mRNA destruction or translational repression, based on the complementarity degree with target mRNA sequences (15, 16). In cancer cells, aberrantly produced miRNA disrupts intracellular RNA networks. Abnormally expressed miRNAs contribute significantly to cancer cell malignancy, such as breast cancer (BC). Different biological mechanisms of BC progression, such as cell proliferation, migration, invasion, metastasis, cancer recurrence, apoptotic response, and chemoresistance, are regulated by either oncogenic miRNAs (oncomiRs) or tumor suppressor miRNAs (tsmiR) (17). For example, tumor suppressive *miR-1275* was discovered to prevent BC growth by targeting *DVL3*, *PPP2R2D*, *THSD4*, *CREB1*, *SYT7*, and *PRKACA* (14). Also, we previously found that *miR-4510* suppressed breast cancer growth by targeting *TP53*, *TP53INP1*, *MMP11*, and *COL1A1* (7). *MiR-374a*, on the other hand, promotes tumor dissemination and progression by inhibiting *LACTB* and indicates an unfavorable prognosis in breast cancer (18). Furthermore, *miR-17-5p* was revealed to be a unique predictor of breast cancer recurrence. Previous research found that *miR-638* was a key regulator in the onset and progression of human malignancies. For example, *miR-638* was discovered to inhibit stomach cancer carcinogenesis (19). A study showed that *MicroRNA let-7a* reduces breast cancer cell migration and invasion by downregulating C-C chemokine receptor type 7 (20). *MiR-132* inhibits spread, invasion, movement, and recurrence in breast cancer via targeting *HNI*(21). Another study revealed that the *miR-1185-2-3p-GOLPH3L* network regulates glucose metabolism in carcinoma of the breast by regulating *p53*-induced *SERPINE1* (22). This microRNA was found to trigger endothelial cell death by inhibiting *UVRAG* and *KRIT1* (23). There have been no studies on the role of *miR-1185-5p* in breast carcinoma. In colorectal cancer, SIRT1-mediated expression of *CD24* and epigenetic inhibition of the novel tumor suppressor *miR-1185-1* enhances colorectal cancer stemness (24).

The role of this microRNA has not fully understood in biological processes of the BC. Therefore, the objective of this study was to conduct research into the role of *miR-1185-5p* expression level as a novel biomarker for breast cancer diagnosis, and to show how *miR-1185-5p* regulates breast cancer by targeting some genes, including *BCAS1*, *CASC3*, *GATA2* and *VOPPI*.

Materials and Methods

Sample collection

The experimental tissues were obtained from Rizgary Teaching Hospital from 150 patients with breast cancer and 150 non-cancerous women. The tissues were preserved in an 80 °C refrigerator after being frozen in liquid nitrogen. The Salahaddin University-Erbil Ethics Committee accepted this study. All procedures used in the study were also in conformity with the 1964 Helsinki Declaration, and all research participants provided written informed consent and permission for publication. A questionnaire was used to collect pathological characteristics from 150 patients. Table 1 shows the characteristics.

Table 1. Cohort summary

Feature	Participants (%)	<i>miR-1185-5p</i>		<i>P</i> value
		<i>High</i>	<i>Low</i>	
Age				0.21
≤50	83 (55.3)	39	44	
>50	67 (44.7)	30	37	
BMI				0.01*
18.5-24.9	25 (16.7)	5	20	
25.0-29.9	80 (53.3)	21	50	
30.0 or higher	45 (30)	10	30	
Tumor size				0.04*
< 3cm	48 (32)	8	40	
≥3cm	102 (68)	28	84	
Tumor grade				0.01*
I	15 (10)	5	10	
II	30 (20)	8	22	
III	105 (70)	27	78	
Lymph node metastasis				0.042*
No	46 (30.7)	5	41	
Yes	104 (69.3)	23	81	
Lymphatic invasion				0.022*
Yes	110 (73.3)	23	81	
No	40 (26.7)	8	32	
Venous invasion				0.01*
Yes	110 (73.3)	13	97	
No	40 (26.7)	9	31	
Biomarkers				0.42
Triple-negative	45 (30)	12	33	
ER+ & PR+	60 (40)	17	43	
ER- & PR-	12 (8)	2	10	
ER+ & HER2+	33 (22)	13	20	
Ki67 status				0.04*
Yes	135 (135)	29	106	
No	0 (0)		0	
Not available	15 (10)	0	13	

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BMI; Body mass index. **ER**; Estrogen. **PR**; Progesterone. **HER**; human epidermal growth factor receptor 2. Statistical analyses were executed via the χ^2 test. *; $P < 0.05$ was reckoned as significant

Total RNA extraction and library preparation

In this research, Massive Analysis of cDNA Ends (MACE-Seq) was applied to generate a single read per transcript molecule. Short and different transcripts were therefore identified at twenty times lower sequencing depth than regular RNA-Seq, with no need for length-based normalization. Total RNA expression profiling of 50 breast cancer (BC) and 50 normal adjacent tissue (NAT) were analysed in this research. The practical portion of this work was carried out in the GenXPro GmbH laboratory in Germany. Total RNA extraction, small RNA separation, and small RNA library preparation were done. Total RNA was firstly extracted from ten μm of each BC and normal tissues for each sample using the MACE-seq kit (GenXPro GmbH, Frankfurt, Germany). TrueQuant SmallRNA-NGS Kit includes all of the reagents needed to isolate non-coding (nc) RNA from protein-coding RNA transcripts. Because transcripts contain a class of similar small RNAs (sRNAs) such as microRNAs (miRNAs), small nucleolar RNAs (snoRNAs), small interfering RNAs (siRNAs), small nuclear RNAs (snRNAs), small rDNA-derived RNA (srRNA) and PIWI-interacting RNAs (piRNAs). For better quantification, Unique Molecular Identifier kit (UMI, also known as Molecular Barcoding or TrueQuant Adapter) was used to label PCR-template molecules before their amplification. Each template is subsequently detected by a unique combination of the TrueQuant sequence and the template sequence. After PCR amplification, The products can be observed and isolated from the dataset, allowing for virtually total elimination of uneven amplification and artifacts formed during the PCR. Libraries, including coding-RNA and non-coding RNA libraries, were built for total RNA fragments from the BC and NAT samples. TrueQuant (GenXPro GmbH, Frankfurt, Germany) was used to reverse the total transcripts, followed by indexing-PCR, amplification. The SuperScript® III First-Strand Synthesis System (GenXPro GmbH, Frankfurt, Germany) was used to generate first and second-strand cDNA. Then the fragments were purified by Solid-phase reversible immobilization or SPRI bead from other reagents. After quality control of the library, library quantification, and pooling, The indexed libraries were sequenced by the platform of an Illumina Hiseq2000 with 1×100 bps. Small RNAs, those which are between 16-25 bps, were selected from whole RNA molecules using the flashPAGETM Fractionator System (Life Technologies) to prepare microRNA (miRNA) libraries. TrueQuant barcodes of P3 and P5 were directly ligated to short RNAs after purifying small RNAs, as described by Hafner and colleagues (25). The miRNA group was sequenced using an Illumina Hiseq machine. The ordered reads were trimmed out for high-quality sequences to remove flanking

P3 and P5 barcodes. Following this, the tool Bowtie 2 was used to align the sorted reads to the reference sequences and annotate with matching attributes (26). The HT-seq tool was used to quantify the number of mapped reads to each gene (27). The differential expression analysis was carried out using DESeq2, which is likewise based on negative binomial generalized linear models (28). The findings were collated into a final table that included significance criteria such as *P* value, (False discovery range) FDR, and log₂Fold-Changes. R-scripts for analyzing and visualizing of the significantly up and down-regulated genes in the Final Data were run on R-studio software (Version: 2023.12.0+369, Released: 2024-01-10).

RT-qPCR Analysis

MiR-1185-5p, previously unstudied in BC, was chosen from the MACE-seq results to further confirm its differential expression in 200 samples (100 BC tissues and 100 NAT) using the Real Time-quantitative polymerase chain reaction (RT-qPCR) technology. These samples were overlapped with 50 pairs used in MACE-Seq. This task's practical part was performed at Salahuddin University Research Center (SURC). In each experiment, 10µm from the tissue sample was placed in a microcentrifuge tube. A PowerGen 125 Tissue Homogenizer was then used to homogenize the tissue pellet. Total extracted RNA molecules were isolated using the NORGEN BIOTEK CORP (Canada) FFPE RNA/DNA Purification Plus kit (Cat. No. 54300). The miRNA All-In-One cDNA Synthesis Kit (Cat. No. G898, Applied Biological Materials Inc./ABM, US) was applied to construct complementary DNA (cDNA) at 45 °C for 50 minutes.

Determination of differential expression of *miR-1185-5p*

All RT-qPCR procedure materials were purchased from ABM(United States). To amplify the targeted miRNA among total cDNA molecules, the total qPCR reaction for each well was 20 µm, which contained 10 µm of BrightGreen miRNA qPCR MasterMix-ROX (Cat. No. MasterMix-mR), 0.5µm of forward and reverse primers (Cat. No. MPH01027), 2 µm of template cDNA, and 7.5 µm of nuclease-free water. In addition, two housekeeping miRNA primers, including SNORD44 primers (Cat. No. MPH0003) and U6-2 primers (Cat. No. MPH0001), were employed. GAPDH protein was also a housekeeping protein for each *miR-1185-5p*, *BCAS1*, *CASC3*, *GATA2*, and *VOPPI*. The mRNA expression was calculated using the $2^{-\Delta\Delta ct}$ way. The following 3-step cycle protocol was used to carry out the qPCR reaction. Enzyme activation was performed at 95

°C for 10 minutes, followed by 35 cycles of denaturing at 95 °C for 10 seconds, annealing at 62 °C for 20 seconds, and elongation at 72 °C for 20 seconds.

MicroRNA database-based microRNA Targets

The most prevalent putatively targeted genes that *miR-1185-5p* regulates were found using ten microRNA databases (Figure 3). In this study, four putative targets, including *BCAS1*, *CASC3*, *GATA2*, and *VOPPI*, were found to have *miR-1185-5p* binding sequences. Then, in the MACE-seq results, they were found to have differential expression. The relatively differential expression of these putative genes was analyzed using GraphPad Prism, Version 8.0.1.

Clinicopathological data linked with BC were analyzed.

Association between *miR-1185-5P* and its targets was computationally assessed to determine clinical significance using databases from cBioPortal (<http://www.cbioportal.org/>) and OncoLnc (<http://www.oncolnc.org/>). These sites provided clinical data and expression levels of the *miR-1185-5P* and its target genes, which were then retrieved on February 10, 2024. Overall Survival (OS) were examined using Kaplan-Meier analysis (logrank test). $P < 0.05$ indicates a significant difference. The probability of happening per month was then calculated using R studio software. The data and R scripts will be archived for future research.

Culture of cell lines

Iraqi Biotech company provided the MCF-7 cell lines and the human breast epithelial cell line MCF10A. these cells may be seeded in T75 flasks at 1×10^6 cells/flask in low glucose Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM) supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS), 2 mM glutamine, 0.01 mg/ml insulin and 1% penicillin/streptomycin mix and need to be incubated at 37°C in an atmosphere of 5% CO₂.

Transfection of cells

Lipofectamine 2000 (Invitrogen, ABM, US) was applied to transfect *miR-1185-5P* mimics or inhibitors, as well as a control, into MCF-7 cells. For this experiment, transfected cells (4×10^4) were grown in 96-well plates and were then cultured for 0, 24, 48, and 72 hours in an incubator at 37 °C and 5% CO₂. Then, 10 µl of CCK-8 reagent was applied to each well for 2 hours (BIO

laboratory, Erbil, Iraq). Finally, a microplate reader (Molecular Devices) detected the absorbance of each well at 450 nm.

Transwell Assay

Transwell chambers with 8- μ m pores were used to monitor cell migration and invasion. Matrigel (abmgood, USA) was applied to the upper surface to observe cellular invasion. The lower chamber was filled with 10% FBS. MCF-7 cells treated with *miR-1185-5p* mimics or inhibitors were cultured in serum-free media for 48 hours at 37°C and 5% CO₂. Methanol was used to fix the moving cells, which were then stained with crystal violet. The number of eliminated cells was determined using a microscope.

Western Blot Analysis

The Western blot technique was used to determine the expression levels of *BCAS1*, *CASC3*, *GATA2*, and *VOPPI*. These proteins were isolated using RIPA lysis buffer. Then, 10% of SDS-PAGE was applied to separate the target proteins. After blocking the proteins with 5% skim milk, they were transferred to PVDF membranes. The membranes were treated with antibodies against *BCAS1*, *CASC3*, *GATA2*, *VOPPI*, and *GAPDH* overnight at 4°C. The protein was then treated with secondary antibodies for two hours at ambient temperature. Protein expression was measured using the Electro-Chemi-Luminescence system (ECL).

Results

Small non-coding (snc) RNA analysis by TrueQuant adapter

In this research, MACE-Seq technique was used to profile the differential expression of protein-coding and non-coding (nc) RNAs. The TrueQuant adapter was used to reveal differential expression of ncRNA molecules in BC versus normal tissue. Then SAM program screened out 1062 ncRNAs by comparing their expression levels. The DESeq2 package in the R program was used to analyze the differential expression of ncRNAs (DEncRNAs) between BC and normal tissue. In the multtest package, Bonferroni was used to adapt the P-value into the FDR. The cutoff criteria for DEncRNAs were $FDR < 0.05$ and $|\log_2 FC| > 0.5$. The raw data were then normalized and log₂-transformed to construct a volcano plot (Fig. 1A). Each dot in the plot represents a ncRNA. Then, 227 significant microRNAs were separated from 1062 ncRNAs to demonstrate differential expression (Fig. 1B). Among these, 22 miRNA molecules were over-expressed in BC tissue; whereas, 152 miRNAs were down-expressed on the left volcano plot. In this research, we focused on *miR-1186-5p* to further study the role in BC biological processes. TrueQuant results showed that *miR-1186-5p* was significantly down-regulated in the BC. Pvalue was $P = 0.01$, as shown in Figure 1B. Furthermore, the significantly decreased expression of this was confirmed by the RT-qPCR method. Pvalue was 0.001 figure 1C. Kaplan-Meier curve showed that the downregulation of *miR-101-5p* was significantly related to poor prognosis in patients with BC (overall survival (OS) rate: $P = 0.002$) (Figure 1D).

To determine the role of *miR-1186-5p* as a post-transcriptional regulator of gene products, we were deeply studied by different molecular techniques in BC and normal tissues.

Figure 1 (A) Comparison of differential expression of non-coding (nc)RNAs in BC with normal tissues. (B) MiR-1185-5p identification in the expression of MACE-Seq. (C) Validation of miR-1185-5p expression profile by MACE-Seq and RT-qPCR in BC and normal. (D) The overall survival analysis of in TCGA for miR-1185-5p

Comparative analysis of DEGs in BC and normal tissues

Beside the small (s)RNA molecules, MACE-Seq was used to identify differentially expressed genes (DEGs) in 50 BC patients, and compared them to 50 normal tissues. A total of 27,022 protein-coding RNAs were differentially expressed. $P < 0.05$ were considered significant. SAM program was used to filter out these genes. Scatter plot showed that 8,042 protein-coding RNAs were normalized and log₂-transformed. Approximately, 5,120 genes were significantly down-regulated, while 2,922 genes were significantly up-regulated in BC when compared to normal (Figure 2A).

Figure 2 (A) Comparison of differentially expressed genes in BC with normal by MACE-Seq method. 8,042 genes shown (27,022 total, $P < 0.05$). 5,120 genes were down regulated, 2,922 up regulated in BC. (B) Comparison of differential expression of miR-1185-5p-associated proteins in BC with normal

***BCAS1*, *CASC3*, *GATA2*, and *VOPPI* are putative target genes for miRNA-1185-5p**

With the help application of ten computational target predictions, the major targets of *miR-1185-5p* was determined among the MACE-seq results, In this experiment four genes were determined to have complementary sites with the 3' untranslated region (UTR), including *BCAS1*, *CASC3*, *GATA2*, and *VOPPI*(Figure 2B). We picked genes that appeared in at least seven out of ten databases and were expected to have a complimentary area with the chosen miRNA(Figure 3). The results were then filtered to focus on genes associated with BC. We discovered that *BCAS1*, *CASC3*, *GATA2*, and *VOPPI* might be target genes for *miR-1185-5p* (Figure 3). Eight databases indicated that the *BCAS1* mRNA was targeted by *miR-1185-5p*;. In contrast, nine databases revealed that *GATA2* gene has the binding site to *miR-1185-5p*, but *CASC3* and *VOPPI* genes were confirmed in nine putative target databases to be targeted by *miR-1185-5p*.

Figure 3

Determining the expression level of putative target genes in MACE-seq results

In MACE-seq, four putative target genes (*BCAS1*, *CASC3*, *GATA2*, and *VOPP1*) were identified and designated in BC cells compared to normal tissue (Figure 2B). Figure 4 demonstrated the differential expression of which proteins and their binding sites to *miR-1185-5p*. The MACE-Seq results showed that the identified target genes were significantly overexpressed in BC when compared to normal tissues.

Figure 4 Genes of *BCAS1*, *CASC3*, *GATA2*, and *VOPP1* were putative targets of *miR-1185-5p* in BC. (A) *miR-1185-5p* binds to the 3'UTR of these genes. SNP in *miR-1185-5p* binding site and Location of the target sites for *miR-1185-5p* in the 3'UTR of these genes. (B) Comparison of differential expression of *miR-1185-5p*-associated proteins in BC with normal by MACE-Seq.

DNA Sequencing analysis

In order to detect single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) in the identified miRNAs. For 50% of the samples, DNA sequencing was performed. The result showed that pre-*miR-1185-5p* was 86 nucleotides long, and mature *miR-1185-5p* was 21nts. Compared to normal tissue, the *miR-1185-5p* in BC tissue contained a single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) where Adenine (A) was altered to Guanine (G) at 101,044,217 on chromosome 14. The SNP was found inside the *miR-1185-5p* seed region where miRNA binds to 3'UTR of the target gene, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Schematics representation of genomic structure analysis of miR-1185 genes. (A) Chromosomal locus and miR-1185 gene location (B) Alignment sequence of pre-miR-1185-5p in BC compared to Normal. Single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) in the pre-miRNA-1185 sequence in miR-1185-p5 binding site can occur in BC, compared to normal. (C) stem-loop structure of miR-1185-5p in BC.

Breast cancer progression inhibited by *miR-1185-5p* overexpression

In this experiment, MCF-7 cell lines was used to detect the *miR-1185-5p* expressions. Reduced expression of *miR-1185-5p* was observed in MCF-7 cell lines. Next, MCF-7 cells were transfected with *miR-1185-5p* mimics or inhibitors to investigate its function in breast cancer. Transfection efficiency was assessed using RT-qPCR. Overexpression of *miR-1185-5p* decreased breast cancer cell proliferation (Fig. 7). In contrast, knocking down *miR-1185-5p* increased MCF-7 cell proliferation (Fig. 7D). The increased expression of *miR-1185-5p* inhibited cell migration; whereas, knocking it out drove migration in MCF-7 cells (Fig. 7). The increased expression of *miR-1185-5p* was found to decrease the progression of breast cancer.

Figure 6 The increased expression of miR-1185-5p slows the progression of breast cancer. (A) MCF-7 cell lines express miR-1185-5p. (B) The expression of miR-1185-5p was evaluated in MCF-7 cells using miR-1185-5p mimics or inhibitors. (C) Cell proliferation was assessed using miR-1185-5p mimics or inhibitors. (D, E) Analysis of migration and invasion of cells using miR-1185-5p mimics or inhibitors. *** $P < 0.001$.

MiR-1185-5P can directly bind to *BCAS1*, *CASC1*, *GATA2*, and *VOPPI* in breast cancer.

This experiment revealed the downstream target of miR-1185-5p. Ten computational prediction programs identified binding sites for miR-638 in four predicted genes, including *BCAS1*, *CASC1*, *GATA2*, and *VOPPI* (Figure 7A). We also discovered that miR-1185-5p mimics decreased *BCAS1*, *CASC3*, *GATA2*, and *VOPPI* expression (Figure 7B), while miR-638 inhibitors increased *BCAS1*, *CASC3*, *GATA2*, and *VOPPI* expression in MCF-7 cells. *MiR-1185-5p* inhibits the expression of *BCAS1*, *CASC3*, *GATA2*, and *VOPPI* in breast cancer by binding directly to *BCAS1*, *CASC3*, *GATA2*, and *VOPPI*.

Figure 7 Genes of *BCAS1*, *CASC3*, *GATA2*, and *VOPPI* were a direct target of miR-1185-5p in breast cancer: (A) These genes had binding sites with miR-1185-5p. (B) The *BCAS1*, *CASC3*, *GATA2*, and *VOPPI* expression was observed in MCF-7 cells containing miR-1185-5p mimics or inhibitor. * $P < 0.01$, ** $P < 0.01$, *** $P < 0.001$.

Western Bolt analysis

We explored how *miR-1185-5p* affects the expression of *BCAS1*, *CASC3*, *GATA2*, and *VOPPI*. Upregulation of *miR-1185-5p* reduced *BCAS1*, *CASC3*, *GATA2*, and *VOPPI* expression, while downregulation of *miR-1185-5p* had the reverse effect. In addition, overexpression of *miR-1185-5p* decreased the expression of *BCAS1*, *CASC3*, *GATA2*, and *VOPPI* (Figure 8), whereas downregulation increased the expression of these genes.

Discussion

Breast cancer (BC) rates have increased globally since the late 1970s. Although Iraqi Kurdistan does not have a high prevalence of BC, it is not recommended to be overly optimistic. Iraqi Kurdistan has had a 1-2% increase in breast cancer incidence compared to countries with high rates (19). As a result, people are increasingly concerned about BC. Recently, a growing number of microRNA (miR) expression levels have been discovered to be associated with breast cancer progression through regulation of numerous protein-coding and non-coding genes. The differential expression profiling of microRNA molecules have been analyzed via multiple high-throughput techniques, such as small RNA-Seq, MACE-sequencing (14), NGS-based array, and RNA-sequencing (29), are now accessible and have produced microRNA expression profiles of BC, indicating the differential expression of multiple miRNAs. Detecting differential expression of miRNAs, as demonstrated in multiple investigations, is one method for determining the most important miRNA from a large number of miRNAs. Several studies have indicated that several miRNAs, such as *miR-1275*, *miR-107*, *miR-205-3p*, *miR-100*, *miR-122*, and *miR-99a-5p*, are continuously down-expressed and operate as tumor-suppressive miRNA in BC cells (7). In this study, down-expression of *miR-1185-5p* in breast cancer was detected and *miR-1185-5p* suppressed the breast cancer progression.

MiRNAs regulate gene expression in cells, hence controlling biological processes such as differentiation, migration, invasion, proliferation, and metastasis. Over the past decade, research has shown that miRNA malfunction is a primary cause of tumor growth. Downregulation of miR-638 in breast cancer is associated with a poor prognosis. *MiR-638* can decrease malignant activity in breast cancer cells by targeting *HOXA9* (30). *MiR-17* and *miR-19a* levels decreased from early to advanced stages of breast cancer, suggesting their potential for utility in diagnostic and disease monitoring. This indicated that downregulation of these miRNAs contributed to breast cancer staging and illness prognosis; thus, their expression profiles are useful in multiplex detection for diagnostic and prognostic purposes in breast cancer. Similarly, increasing overexpression of these miRNAs as a breast cancer therapeutic technique gives a promising avenue for further research into gene expression patterns (31). Downregulation of circ_0009910 was linked with upregulation of *miR-145-5p* and downregulation of MUC1 expression in breast cancer cells (32). Using dual-luciferase reporter assays, a study confirmed the interactions between many anticipated miRNA-

mRNA pairs (*oar-miR-133-HDAC1*, *miR-1185-5p-MYH1/HADHA/OXCT1*, and *PC-5p-3703_578-INSR/ACTG1*) that may alter skeletal muscle development. In this investigation, we found *miRNA-1185-5p*, *BCAS1*, *CASC3*, *GATA2*, and *VOPPI* in the BC at various embryonic stages, revealing that a number of putative miRNA-mRNA pairings might function as BC development modulators (33). In the miRNA-hub gene network, *miR-1185-5p* and hsa-miR-3679-5p may suppress the expression of *IGLL5* as rheumatoid arthritis advances. In this study, down-expression of *miR-1185-5p* was related to worse prognosis in breast cancer patients. In previous studies, low *miR-1185-5p* expression was found in colon carcinoma and related to its clinical significance (34).

Conclusion

The present study examined the differential expression levels of protein-coding RNA and non-coding RNA molecules in 50 cancerous cases versus 50 normal cases. The downregulation of *miR-1185-5p* was evaluated using the RT-qPCR technique. Down-expression promotes breast cancer by boosting the activity of biological processes such as migration, and invasion. Upregulated *miR-1185-5p* inhibited BC formation by influencing the direct expression of *BCAS1*, *CASC3*, *GATA2*, and *VOPPI*. This is the first study to indicate that *miR-1185-5p* functions as a tumor-suppressive miRNA in BC cells, regulating several targets closely associated with BC pathogenesis and oncogenesis.

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Author contribution

Dr. Sevan O. Majeed was responsible for the experimental design. He led to the execution of the experiments. Although analyses of MACE-sequencing and sRNA sequencing were done in

GenXpro company, in Germany. Data analysis and bioinformatic tasks were done by him also discussed and interpreted the data and also did the manuscript mapping and submission. He supervised the project.

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Availability of data and materials

Although raw data of MACE-sequencing may be available in the database of GenXpro, at (<https://genxpro.net/>, available project: 20190618_Majed_MACE SMajed 2019-06-18 18:44:18.841903+00:00), These data will be further studied for another research in the future. The findings described in this manuscript were provided by Dr. Sevan O. Majed.

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Prior to the study, all methods done in this study including human participants and human materials were approved by Human Research Ethics Committee (HREC) at Science College in Salahuddin University-Erbil. All methods while performing the study were also performed in accordance with the 1964 Helsinki Declaration and the written informed-consent and Permission for the publication were obtained from all research participants.

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Competing interest

The author announces no conflict of interest. Dr. Sevan is a teacher of Salahaddin University-Erbil, a subsidiary of ministry of higher education in Kurdistan region government (KRG).

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